

Highlights

Extreme Weakly Supervised Binary Semantic Image Segmentation via One-Pixel Supervision

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- Binary segmentation with sparse one-pixel annotations, even a single one per dataset.
- Our method operates without requiring background annotations.
- Novel contrastive loss using class-of-interest one-pixel annotations.
- Dynamic contrastive loss hyperparameter computation based on image features.

Extreme Weakly Supervised Binary Semantic Image Segmentation via One-Pixel Supervision

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Abstract

Despite recent advancements, Unsupervised Semantic Segmentation (USS) methods still exhibit a significant performance deficit compared to supervised approaches, particularly in binary semantic segmentation. This limitation arises because, without supervision, USS methods struggle to distinguish foreground from background image regions, particularly when the foreground contains small or uncommon objects. This issue is addressed by our proposed Extremely Weakly Supervised Binary Semantic Segmentation (EWS) framework. EWS expects minimal supervision, consisting only of a small set of one-pixel annotations explicitly belonging to the foreground class across the entire image dataset. Our approach leverages these one-pixel annotations and employs two contrastive losses to map visual transformer features into well-separated foreground and background feature clusters. Additionally, we propose a novel loss function to eliminate the need for hyperparameter tuning of the contrastive loss threshold, by dynamically computing it based on the similarity between the input image features. Even if we employ a single one-pixel annotation, EWS achieves competitive results in binary segmentation tasks while maintaining low computational costs, making it an efficient solution for critical segmentation applications.

Keywords: Binary semantic segmentation, One-Pixel Annotations, Contrastive learning

1. Introduction

Unsupervised Semantic Segmentation (USS) typically refers to the problem of image segmentation without depending on annotated datasets. State-of-the-art USS meth-

ods [1, 2, 3] are either based on or are extensions of the STEGO method [1]. The STEGO method extracts image features by employing a pretrained foundational Vision Transformer (ViT) using the DINO framework [4, 5] and thereby minimizes a contrastive loss function, to extract refined features. This process effectively utilizes the correspondences between feature vectors to project them into low dimensionality representation that can naturally form cluster, thus leading to highly accurate semantic image segmentation. Despite the improved USS capabilities, several limitations persist. Notably, USS methods are less effective than their supervised counterparts, as the performance gap becomes significantly larger when segmentation ground truth is available, particularly in binary segmentation. Additionally, their deployment still requires supervised post-processing to map the produced unlabeled segmented regions, into class-labeled ones.

In a dataset containing various objects, the unsupervised semantic segmentation of a specific object of interest becomes challenging. This issue is particularly hard to solve for small objects, as USS models tend to segment the two most prevalent and visually dominant objects, as illustrated in the USS segmentation mask depicted in Fig. 1. Therefore, semantic segmentation methods often rely on more annotation-intensive approaches, such as one shot learning [6, 7, 8], or weakly supervised learning methods [9, 10, 11]. One-shot learning methods require a query image and its corresponding segmentation mask to detect the object of interest in a new input image during inference. Despite this advantage, such methods have significant limitations. They are often highly biased toward the training classes, which can lead to incorrect object predictions and, consequently to a low recall rate. Furthermore, retraining or optimizing one-shot learning models is time-consuming as they requires annotated datasets, making them less practical for many real-world applications. Alternatively, state-of-the-art weakly supervised learning approaches, such as those leveraging multimodal CLIP [12], rely on class-related text annotations (e.g., the label ‘car’ for Fig. 1) to generate class-of-interest pseudo-masks. However, since these masks are initially generated through methods such as GradCAM [13], they often lack fine-grained image region details.

We aim to address these limitations by building upon the STEGO framework with minimal supervision. In our framework, we hypothesize that the least time-consuming

Figure 1: This visualization demonstrates an example of vehicle segmentation. It illustrates how the USS method segments only the two most common classes in the dataset, while our EWS pipeline, utilizing just two annotated pixels, achieves results comparable to fully supervised semantic segmentation methods.

and minimally supervised annotation strategy involves providing just a few one-pixel annotations labeled for the class of interest, potentially even a single one in the entire image dataset to be segmented. We call this framework Extremely Weekly Supervised (EWS) semantic segmentation. Its key idea is that the feature vectors from the ViT feature map corresponding to the provided pixel annotations can function as class prototypes. By computing the cosine similarity between a class prototype and the feature map, we obtain a class similarity map that highlights regions sharing similar characteristics. Unlike USS methods, where identifying the most representative class prototypes is inherently challenging, our approach ensures access to at least one prototype. The derived class prototypes can be used to enhance image features and segmentation performance.

In the case of binary semantic segmentation high quality masks can be produced, if the enhanced feature map satisfies two properties: a) it can provide fine-grained segmentation details, while b) it can ensure that the enhanced feature vectors space can be decomposed into two clusters, corresponding to foreground and background, respectively. Balancing these feature map requirements is highly challenging, as they contradict each other. We can efficiently resolve this conflict by projecting the ViT features onto two distinct feature maps, one for the image foreground and the other for the background, from which we can derive the foreground and background similarity maps, respectively. To train the background feature map, we developed a novel contrastive loss which utilizes the class prototypes. This way, the feature vectors of the

background feature map are encouraged to take only two representations based on their similarity to the class prototypes, thereby ensuring a clear separation between the feature vectors of the background and foreground. However, since all background objects are constrained to adopt a single representation, this can lead to incorrectly high background similarity values in foreground regions. This limitation is addressed by utilizing the foreground feature map, which incorporates both STEGO and our contrastive loss to extract richer image features, thereby yielding a more accurate foreground similarity map. Consequently, these feature maps, along with class prototypes, are processed to generate the foreground and background similarity maps. Following the comparison of these maps at each location, the final binary semantic segmentation mask is obtained.

Furthermore, the contrastive loss function proposed in STEGO requires tuning of a hyperparameter threshold. If the similarity between two feature vectors exceeds this threshold, they are projected closer together, otherwise, they are projected further apart. However, having a fixed threshold for any feature vector pair is a significant limitation. For example, image patches belonging to different objects can be incorrectly projected close to each other. This challenge can be addressed by hyperparameter threshold tuning using the image dataset ground truths or human supervision to identify the threshold value that maximizes the USS model segmentation accuracy. However, such ground truth may be unavailable. To address this limitation, we propose a novel process that allows dynamic threshold determination for each image patch based on its feature similarity to other image patches.

The streamlined EWS pipeline achieves exceptional binary semantic segmentation performance using only a single or a few one-pixel foreground annotations for the entire image dataset, without hyperparameter threshold tuning nor background annotations. This approach allows rapid image segmentation model deployment. Furthermore, as the ViT parameters remain frozen and the additional EWS pipeline components have few parameters, incorporating new classes into EWS incurs minimal inference costs, thus ensuring scalability and efficiency.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- A novel pipeline for Extreme Weakly supervised binary semantic Segmentation

is proposed that enables efficient image semantic segmentation with minimal supervision.

- A new dynamic computation of a contrastive loss hyperparameter threshold is provided that is applicable across all STEGO-based architectures, thus eliminating the need for manual parameter tuning.
- A comprehensive ablation study demonstrates the impact of a varying number of one-pixel annotations on segmentation accuracy.

2. Related Work

2.1. Unsupervised Semantic Segmentation

Training semantic segmentation models requires pixel-level annotations, which is a costly and time-intensive process, particularly for large datasets. To address this labeling challenge USS methods, such as IIC [14], leverage mutual information between paired data samples to achieve semantic pixel clustering and region segmentation without using image ground truths. PiCIE [15] builds upon this approach by introducing an inductive bias, applying invariance to photometric effects and equivariance to geometric transformations. RVCC [16] introduces robust virtual class contrast by clustering foreground pixels into pseudo virtual classes thereby improving unsupervised segmentation of complex objects. More recently, state-of-the-art unsupervised semantic segmentation architectures have employed the Visual Transformer (ViT) [4] pretrained with the DINO framework [5]. DINO ViT produce image features that capture scene layout and provide consistent object representations across different images. STEGO [1] leverages DINO features to map them into lower-dimensional spaces where they form compact clusters, resulting in highly precise semantic segmentation predictions. Meanwhile, HP method [3] that employs contrastive learning to identify task-specific and task-agnostic hidden positives, while propagating gradients to nearby patches to ensure semantic consistency, thereby improving segmentation quality. Lastly, EAGLE method [2] addresses the limitations of inadequate segmentation for diverse and structurally complex objects by focusing on object-centric representation learning.

2.2. *Weakly supervised Semantic Segmentation*

Weakly supervised Semantic Segmentation (WSSS) frameworks [17, 18, 19] often generate Class Activation Maps (CAMs) [20, 21, 22] from image-level labels to propose segmentation pseudo-masks, which are then refined to serve as semantic segmentation image ground truths. In contrast, some approaches [23, 24] directly use these pseudo-masks as final predictions without requiring the training of a separate segmentation model. Methods like MARS [25] address the issue of false predictions in class-related backgrounds by using a USS model to remove class-related objects from pseudo-masks. Additionally, methods such as SAM [26], can be exploited for producing pseudo-masks with high-quality object boundaries [11, 18, 27] or CLIP [12] for improved object region activation [28]. SemPLoS further advances WSSS by introducing Contrastive Prompt Learning and Prompt-guided Semantic Refinement [10]. It leverages the CLIP latent space to automatically discover prompts, suppress co-occurring background regions, and generate precise segmentation pseudo-masks. CLIP-ES also leverages CLIP zero-shot capabilities, while incorporating text-driven strategies and class-aware attention-based refinement [9]. It efficiently generates pseudo-masks with minimal supervision and without additional training.

2.3. *Zero and One Shot Semantic Segmentation*

Few-shot semantic segmentation aims to segment unseen classes using only a few examples. In Zero-Shot semantic segmentation [29, 30, 31], these examples are often word embeddings, while in One-Shot segmentation [32, 33, 34], they include a segmentation mask highlighting the object of interest. Zero-Shot methods leverage CLIP’s generalization capabilities for segmentation tasks. For instance, ZSSEG [35] groups pixels into clusters and uses CLIP to classify these regions, while MaskCLIP [36] employs CLIP visual and text encoders to classify patches and produce segmentation masks at inference. Its enhanced version MaskCLIP+ [36], uses these masks as pseudo-labels for self-training. CLIPSeg [6] extends CLIP, to segmentation by integrating a transformer-based decoder to generate binary masks conditioned on text or image prompts, enabling flexible and efficient segmentation across referring expressions, zero-shot, and one-shot settings. In contrast, SegGPT [8], which achieves

state-of-the-art results in one shot learning, introduces a generalist model that unifies diverse segmentation tasks and datasets through in-context visual learning. It leverages a Painter-based framework [7] and a novel random coloring scheme, SegGPT performs a wide range of segmentation tasks—including semantic, instance, panoptic, and video object segmentation—using in-context prompts and feature ensemble strategies for enhanced generalization and flexibility prompts and feature ensemble strategies for enhanced generalization and flexibility.

3. EWS

EWS refers to the problem of unsupervised semantic segmentation, with the minimal difference that we assume that a set of one-pixel annotations (could be a single one) is also available during training. This is a reasonable assumption, and is very valuable in many image segmentation problems, such as fire segmentation, whenever the desired classes that our model must segment are known a-priori. In the following subsection, we describe in detail all the necessary components of the proposed method.

3.1. Prototype Generation

As image feature extractor, we employ the pretrained DINO model, which incorporates Vision Transformer (ViT) network as its backbone. During EWS training, we freeze the ViT parameters, as the self-supervised pretraining ensures that object representations remain consistent across different images, offering strong generalization and semantic capabilities. Given an input image $I \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$, ViT divides it into non-overlapping $p \times p$ pixel image patches, forming a sequence of a $N = \frac{HW}{p^2}$ input tokens. Each patch is then flattened and projected into a D -dimensional space. For a given image input I , ViT outputs a feature map $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$, where the i -th row $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^D$ of matrix \mathbf{X} contains the representations of the i -th image patch.

In our EWS framework, we assume that one-pixel annotations in the form of $[x, y]^T$ exist in a sample of images pointing to the object of interest (e.g., fire). Then, we select the corresponding image patches containing these pixels, to extract their corresponding feature vectors from \mathbf{X} . We refer to these vectors as class prototypes $\mathbf{x}_{p_i} \in \mathbb{R}^D$.

These prototype vectors form the class prototype matrix $\mathbf{X}_p = [\mathbf{x}_{p_1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{p_K}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times D}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$, where K represents the number of one-pixel annotations in the entire dataset.

3.2. EWS Segmentation Pipeline

The cosine similarity between a class prototype feature vector and a patch feature vector serves as a quantitative estimation of class presence within the patch. This similarity score, ranging from $[-1, 1]$, provides a single scalar value that indicates the degree to which the patch corresponds to the given class. Throughout this work, we utilize the fully pairwise cosine similarity function to compute the patch feature similarity between feature matrices. Therefore, given two feature maps $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times D}$, we apply ℓ_2 -normalization, ensuring each row has unit norm. Hereafter, whenever we refer to feature vectors and feature maps used for cosine similarity computation, we refer to their normalized versions, unless stated otherwise. The pairwise cosine similarity function is used to calculate the cosine similarity matrix:

$$\mathbf{C}_{XY} = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{Y}^T, \quad (1)$$

where entry $[\mathbf{C}_{XY}]_{i,j}$ contains the cosine similarity between the i -th row of \mathbf{X} and the j -th row of \mathbf{Y} .

The proposed EWS segmentation pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 1. Given an input image I , we employ the Vision Transformer (ViT) to obtain the feature map \mathbf{X} , which is projected into two lower dimensionality feature spaces, corresponding to the foreground and the background, respectively. To this end, we train two linear layers with weights $\mathbf{W}_f, \mathbf{W}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D'}$, in order to project the unnormalized feature map \mathbf{X} , producing $\mathbf{Z}_f = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{W}_f$ and $\mathbf{Z}_b = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{W}_b$, where $\mathbf{Z}_f, \mathbf{Z}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D'}$, respectively.

To effectively utilize the class prototypes, we first compute the projected foreground prototype matrix using $\mathbf{P}_f = \mathbf{X}_p \mathbf{W}_f$, $\mathbf{P}_f \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times D'}$. Each row $\mathbf{p}_{f_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{D'}$ is a lower dimensionality representation of the class prototype \mathbf{x}_{p_i} . Subsequently, the global foreground prototype $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_f \in \mathbb{R}^{D'}$ is defined as the mean of the projected prototypes:

$$\bar{\mathbf{p}}_f = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbf{p}_{f_i}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: EWS segmentation pipeline.

By exploiting the class prototypes, we use them to calculate a foreground similarity vector $\mathbf{y}_f \in \mathbb{R}^N$:

$$\mathbf{y}_f = \mathbf{Z}_f \bar{\mathbf{p}}_f. \quad (3)$$

Then, the vector entry y_{f_i} which is the least similar to the foreground, is employed as the most probable background image patch and is identified as follows:

$$m = \arg \min_{i \in \{1, \dots, N\}} y_{f_i}. \quad (4)$$

Given the index m , we can identify the corresponding background feature vector \mathbf{z}_{b_m} of matrix \mathbf{Z}_b . We define \mathbf{z}_{b_m} as the global background prototype vector \mathbf{p}_b . The background similarity vector \mathbf{y}_b is subsequently computed as the similarity between $\mathbf{p}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{D'}$ and the matrix $\mathbf{Z}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D'}$ rows:

$$\mathbf{y}_b = \mathbf{Z}_b \mathbf{p}_b. \quad (5)$$

Considering that, we can generate the final background/foreground segmentation vector $\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}^N$, using the calculated foreground and background similarity vectors \mathbf{y}_f , \mathbf{y}_b : an image path $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is assigned to foreground/background depending on

which vector entry y_{b_i}, y_{f_i} is maximal. Finally, the segmentation vector \mathbf{y} is reshaped and upsampled into the segmentation mask $\mathbf{Y} \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$ with a spatial resolution matching that of the input image.

3.3. EWS Training

In the absence of ground truth annotations for the training images, the optimization of the projection weights \mathbf{W}_f and \mathbf{W}_b is guided by contrastive loss functions. As the foreground and background similarity vectors are based on cosine similarity, these loss functions are designed to enhance the effectiveness of this concept as they push the cosine similarity between projected image patches feature vectors pairs towards either zero or one. In contrast to \mathbf{Z}_b , where each row feature vector is expected to correspond to either the background or the foreground, \mathbf{Z}_f should ideally provide a unique feature representation for each object in $\mathbb{R}^{D'}$ to better capture object boundaries. This can be achieved using \mathcal{L}_{corr} [1], which involves computing the self-feature similarity matrices of \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Z}_f , denoted as $\mathbf{C}_{XX} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, respectively. Thus, the correlation contrastive loss function \mathcal{L}_{corr} is employed to optimize the foreground projection matrix \mathbf{W}_f , and is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{corr}(\mathbf{W}_f, \beta_{corr}) = -\frac{1}{N^2} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N ([\mathbf{C}_{XX}]_{ij} - \beta_{corr}) \cdot [\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f}]_{ij}, \quad (6)$$

where $[\mathbf{C}_{XX}]_{ij}$ represent the cosine similarity between feature vectors of \mathbf{X} at rows i and j . To minimize the contrastive loss, the elements of $\mathbf{C}_{XX} - \beta_{corr}$ and $\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f}$ must align in sign. Specifically, when $[\mathbf{C}_{XX}]_{ij} - \beta_{corr}$ is positive, the projected feature similarity $[\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f}]_{ij}$ should take on larger values, while smaller values of $[\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f}]_{ij}$ are encouraged when $[\mathbf{C}_{XX}]_{ij} - \beta_{corr}$ is negative. Additionally, β_{corr} ensures that unrelated patches that exhibit a low positive similarity will not be pushed together.

Although \mathcal{L}_{corr} facilitates the formation of more compact clusters for objects appearing in the training images, it does not incorporate class prototypes. Each prototype \mathbf{x}_p may have a different representation depending on its corresponding pixel annotation. For example, one prototype may target an object such as a “car wheel”, while another may correspond to a “car window”. If our class of interest is the “car”, then

these prototypes must act as a unified entity to ensure that the projected features corresponding to the foreground class belong on the same cluster. Therefore, given the similarity matrix $\mathbf{C}_{XX_p} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$, which represents the similarity between the feature matrix \mathbf{X} and the prototype feature matrix \mathbf{X}_p , the aggregated similarity s_i of image patch i with respect to all prototypes is given by:

$$s_i = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K [\mathbf{C}_{XX_p}]_{ij}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (7)$$

In general, the i -th image patch can be classified as foreground or background based on the sign of $s_i - \beta$. However, directly thresholding in this manner is suboptimal due to the performance sensitivity on the threshold β . Utilizing $s_i - \beta$ in a contrastive loss allows greater flexibility in the choice of β , as the projected features become more robust and generalized through training across many images. To implement the contrastive loss using $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, it is necessary to include a vector in \mathbb{R}^N within the loss function, which will ultimately serve as the final estimation vector for the class of interest. Since the foreground similarity vector has already been defined in Eq. (3), we define the contrastive loss function that incorporates the class prototypes, denoted as \mathcal{L}_{proto} , as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{proto}(\mathbf{W}_f, \beta_{proto}) = -\frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N (s_i - \beta_{proto}) \cdot y_{f_i}, \quad (8)$$

Utilizing the foreground prototype $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_f$ from eq. (2) to produce \mathbf{y}_f , forces all projected prototypes \mathbf{p}_{f_i} to obtain similar representations so that $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_f$ becomes similar to them, thereby maximizing their cosine similarity and minimizing the contrastive loss. Compared to \mathcal{L}_{corr} , applying only \mathcal{L}_{proto} to optimize the linear layer weights may result in a projected feature matrix \mathbf{Z} , where the feature space of the row vectors is divided into two clusters. This encourages all row vectors of \mathbf{Z} associated with the background to converge to the same representation, making this loss well-suited for optimizing the weights of the background linear layer.

By observing the behavior of the two contrastive losses \mathcal{L}_{corr} (6) and \mathcal{L}_{proto} (8), \mathcal{L}_{corr} pushes feature vectors that are similar in the input space, to remain similar in the projected space, while (8) pushes feature vector of the same class (e.g., foreground patches) to become more similar. We apply both losses for the foreground image

patches. The loss function \mathcal{L}_{corr} enhances the object boundaries of \mathbf{Z}_f , while \mathcal{L}_{proto} further pushes the feature vectors corresponding to foreground class closer together, thus reducing incorrect predictions. On the other hand, for background image patches, we only employ \mathcal{L}_{proto} in order facilitate a clear separation between foreground and background, as we do not necessarily need to preserve input space relationships to the projected feature space. Therefore, we define the total foreground loss \mathcal{L}_f and background loss \mathcal{L}_b as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{total} &= \lambda_p \cdot \mathcal{L}_{proto}(\mathbf{W}_f, \beta_{proto}) + \lambda_c \cdot \mathcal{L}_{corr}(\mathbf{W}_f, \beta_{corr}) \\ &+ \lambda_p \cdot \mathcal{L}_{proto}(\mathbf{W}_b, \beta_{proto}), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where the hyperparameters λ_p and λ_c regulate the trade-off between the learning signals. For all experiments, except the ablation study, we set $\lambda_p = \lambda_c = 1$, as this configuration ensures stable and consistent training performance.

3.4. EWS Hyperparameter computation

When implementing the EWS architecture, one significant challenge is the determination of the appropriate hyper-parameters thresholds $\beta_{proto}, \beta_{corr}$. Currently, there are two main approaches: leveraging ground-truth data to identify the threshold that yields the best result, or using statistical properties of the generated matrices [1]. Both approaches can be time-consuming, as they require multiple training runs with various threshold values.

The matrix $\mathbf{C}_{XX} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ measures similarity between image patch features found in matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$. Intuitively, each patch tends to have a few neighbors with a relatively high similarity. Let \mathbf{C}_{XX_i} denote the i -th row vector of \mathbf{C}_{XX} , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The histogram of \mathbf{C}_{XX_i} values typically shows at least two peaks, as depicted in Fig. 3. One peak for patches that belong to the same object or concept, and another peak for unrelated patches. Leveraging this bimodality, we propose a per-patch thresholding scheme to group together image patch features that are likely to belong to the same semantic concept.

Specifically, given a training image and its similarity matrix \mathbf{C}_{XX} , we fit a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to each row \mathbf{C}_{XX_i} values, as illustrated in Fig.(3). The GMM

Figure 3: Dynamic patch threshold computation module. The similarity visualization highlights the relationship between image patches and the i -th patch corresponding to the feature vector \mathbf{x}_i . Using these similarity values, which are fed into a GMM, the clustering visualization illustrates how image patches are grouped and projected closer together.

produces two centroids values that correspond to the two dominant peaks in the similarity distribution; we then take the average of these centroids as the threshold value. Formally, let $g : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote this operation, which returns the mean of the two cluster centroids values. We define $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ as the threshold vector, where the entry b_i corresponds to the threshold for the i -th image patch:

$$b_i = g(\mathbf{C}_{XX_i}). \quad (10)$$

Consequently, the \mathcal{L}_{corr} is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{corr}(\mathbf{W}_f, \mathbf{b}) = -\frac{1}{N^2} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N ([\mathbf{C}_{XX}]_{ij} - b_i) \cdot [\mathbf{C}_{Z_f Z_f}]_{ij}, \quad (11)$$

Each image patch in the training dataset has a unique threshold. For the K foreground annotated image patches, we obtain their corresponding thresholds and set β_{proto} as the average of these threshold values.

4. Experiments

4.1. Dataset

In order to evaluate the proposed EWS methodology and the proposed segmentation architecture, we employ a specialized binary (foreground/background) dataset containing 1135 320×320 pixel forest fire images [37] and the related segmentation ground truth masks. Fire presents a unique segmentation challenge due to its amorphous shape and variable size, making our dataset an excellent testbed for our EWS segmentation methodology. For training purposes, we selectively use only 100 images to demonstrate the efficiency of EWS while minimal data. The remaining 1035 images serve as a test set. Additionally, to accommodate the atypical characteristics of fire, which is consistent across its manifestations, we incorporate the Cityscapes dataset [38] into our study. We adapt this dataset for binary segmentation by isolating one superclass (such as ‘vehicle’, ‘construction’, ‘object’, ‘flat’, ‘sky’, ‘human’, or ‘nature’) in each experiment, utilizing the pre-defined training and validation splits. It is important to note that the segmentation masks are only used for segmentation performance measurement.

4.2. Segmentation Baseline method

To the best of our knowledge, there is no segmentation method that uses the same settings as EWS, i.e., using only few one-pixel annotations to build a model capable of successful binary segmentation. Our main goal in this work is to guide our model to focus on the object of interest, thereby narrowing the performance gap between unsupervised and supervised methods. Therefore, to compare the proposed EWS framework with the state-of-the-art, we need to compare against standard USS and supervised semantic segmentation methods of similar architectures. To this end, we have employed the STEGO method. The standard STEGO method has been trained in the USS case. To showcase the maximum potential of this approach, we also train its supervised version, leveraging annotations in the form of segmentation masks from the training sets.

In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of our novel EWS architecture and compare its segmentation performance, we designed a simple baseline segmentation method

that leverages the same class prototypes utilized in our framework. This approach utilizes the same ViT-Base backbone (21M parameters), pretrained with self-supervision, as in our method, and incorporates the K-means unsupervised clustering head from STEGO, which aims to identify the two most prevalent feature vectors (clusters) in the training set. K-means is applied directly to the feature map produced by the ViT-Base backbone. To adapt this baseline to our scenario, we replace one of the randomly initialized clusters with the average of the prototypes corresponding to the pixel annotations. This ensures that the clustering process is guided toward the object of interest. We refer to this baseline as DINO+Prototypes. By evaluating DINO+Prototypes under the same experimental configurations as EWS, we ensure a fair comparison, as both methods utilize exactly the same prototypes. This allows us to isolate and highlight the contributions of our proposed innovations beyond the use of pixel-level annotations.

Finally, we compare our proposed EWS framework against one-shot learning methods. To this end, we have employed the pretrained SegGPT model. One-shot learning methods can be considered a reasonable comparison to the proposed method, since they only require a single annotated example per class during inference. Here, it should be noted that the proposed EWS protocol only requires single pixel annotations, while training One-shot methods require segmentation masks. However, obtaining such segmentation masks from pixel annotations is relatively easy, as only a single image is sufficient. Nevertheless, to learn how to segment unseen classes based on prompts, these methods require vast amounts of labeled data during training. Additionally, SegGPT employs a supervised pretrained ViT-Large backbone with approximately 307 million parameters, and its input resolution of 448 makes it challenging for real-time performance or deployment on resource-constrained edge devices. Furthermore, the SegGPT training dataset includes several benchmark datasets, with Cityscapes being one of them. Therefore, we exclude SegGPT from the Cityscapes experimental results to avoid an unfair comparison.

4.3. Experimental Setup

To evaluate the robustness of EWS method, we conducted experiments by training it across a variety of configurations. We trained EWS architecture using 1, 4, 8, or 16

CLASS	Points	Images	EWS				DINO+prototypes			
			1	4	8	16	1	4	8	16
Fire	1		62.88 ± 11.35	72.44 ± 4.09	73.36 ± 1.39	72.37 ± 1.65	53.87 ± 10.33	53.72 ± 8.73	57.87 ± 1.98	57.43 ± 1.8
	4		74.5 ± 2.33	77.51 ± 0.87	77.56 ± 1.54	77.68 ± 0.44	58.3 ± 1.12	56.87 ± 0.49	56.78 ± 0.66	56.64 ± 0.7
	8		76.48 ± 0.62	77.62 ± 1.48	78.05 ± 1.33	78.18 ± 0.87	56.96 ± 0.14	56.21 ± 0.2	56.23 ± 0.17	56.15 ± 0.1
	16		77.59 ± 0.53	78.23 ± 0.59	78.03 ± 0.99	77.71 ± 1.21	56.28 ± 0.25	56.0 ± 0.04	56.03 ± 0.1	55.95 ± 0.08
Vehicle	1		74.06 ± 0.81	70.13 ± 5.24	72.85 ± 4.93	69.61 ± 6.41	34.02 ± 1.77	38.62 ± 2.18	38.72 ± 3.14	38.26 ± 3.17
	4		76.59 ± 0.91	78.43 ± 0.92	78.31 ± 0.23	78.53 ± 1.0	36.68 ± 1.61	40.41 ± 2.67	40.21 ± 0.44	39.84 ± 0.77
	8		76.54 ± 1.74	78.26 ± 0.97	78.43 ± 0.51	78.78 ± 0.82	38.82 ± 2.65	41.94 ± 1.5	41.51 ± 1.99	40.62 ± 2.03
	16		74.7 ± 2.84	78.01 ± 0.68	78.15 ± 0.29	78.93 ± 0.11	40.26 ± 1.99	41.62 ± 1.48	42.03 ± 0.8	41.24 ± 1.53
Flat	1		75.01 ± 8.95	83.76 ± 1.23	84.26 ± 1.86	83.72 ± 1.77	85.18 ± 0.62	85.94 ± 0.36	85.7 ± 0.1	86.46 ± 0.13
	4		74.07 ± 1.71	85.1 ± 2.17	84.84 ± 0.46	85.91 ± 0.4	86.17 ± 0.39	86.79 ± 0.47	86.35 ± 0.15	86.64 ± 0.49
	8		81.15 ± 0.94	84.67 ± 2.09	84.63 ± 0.86	85.59 ± 0.19	86.67 ± 0.23	86.79 ± 0.21	86.81 ± 0.05	86.7 ± 0.2
	16		80.91 ± 0.57	85.01 ± 1.12	84.75 ± 0.56	85.65 ± 0.07	86.66 ± 0.27	86.94 ± 0.17	86.84 ± 0.08	86.93 ± 0.11
Construction	1		60.78 ± 1.32	68.45 ± 5.36	68.04 ± 5.11	71.17 ± 3.51	41.64 ± 1.58	41.58 ± 0.71	40.97 ± 0.07	41.18 ± 0.24
	4		68.55 ± 3.44	72.4 ± 1.93	74.5 ± 0.4	74.8 ± 1.8	41.1 ± 0.17	41.38 ± 0.11	41.41 ± 0.15	41.59 ± 0.14
	8		68.96 ± 4.36	73.6 ± 0.33	73.61 ± 0.51	73.21 ± 1.95	41.21 ± 0.11	41.53 ± 0.19	41.4 ± 0.26	41.53 ± 0.11
	16		67.74 ± 7.19	73.74 ± 1.72	72.71 ± 0.91	74.03 ± 1.2	41.49 ± 0.09	41.45 ± 0.1	41.46 ± 0.13	41.63 ± 0.1
Object	1		43.02 ± 2.53	42.5 ± 1.77	49.15 ± 2.23	49.19 ± 2.14	38.2 ± 0.39	39.37 ± 2.05	40.71 ± 1.94	40.52 ± 1.82
	4		49.67 ± 0.09	51.8 ± 0.03	54.12 ± 1.49	54.28 ± 1.54	39.16 ± 0.05	41.1 ± 0.4	42.4 ± 0.9	42.57 ± 0.82
	8		55.68 ± 0.04	55.69 ± 0.35	54.2 ± 2.32	53.7 ± 2.12	42.36 ± 0.13	42.46 ± 0.36	43.15 ± 0.57	43.4 ± 0.42
	16		52.85 ± 0.17	52.9 ± 0.28	53.44 ± 1.75	56.79 ± 0.38	42.31 ± 0.81	43.07 ± 0.83	43.51 ± 0.36	43.68 ± 0.45
Sky	1		65.9 ± 16.84	83.32 ± 1.96	83.56 ± 4.68	84.78 ± 4.05	38.47 ± 2.69	39.96 ± 3.04	40.51 ± 2.04	41.22 ± 1.11
	4		84.61 ± 1.09	84.54 ± 0.78	84.0 ± 0.54	84.15 ± 1.68	41.18 ± 0.34	41.82 ± 0.48	42.02 ± 0.42	42.04 ± 0.37
	8		81.4 ± 6.4	85.66 ± 0.4	85.53 ± 0.98	85.23 ± 1.35	41.93 ± 0.26	42.22 ± 0.24	42.27 ± 0.3	42.39 ± 0.36
	16		85.9 ± 1.22	86.19 ± 0.39	86.08 ± 0.71	86.32 ± 0.67	42.29 ± 0.14	42.33 ± 0.09	42.44 ± 0.13	42.46 ± 0.17
Nature	1		77.66 ± 0.73	81.61 ± 3.06	80.06 ± 3.98	77.55 ± 6.95	39.82 ± 0.06	40.09 ± 0.14	40.17 ± 0.11	40.29 ± 0.12
	4		79.64 ± 0.87	85.33 ± 0.88	86.13 ± 0.73	85.76 ± 0.15	40.12 ± 0.41	40.24 ± 0.37	40.57 ± 0.24	40.32 ± 0.28
	8		83.5 ± 1.93	84.39 ± 0.22	84.11 ± 1.27	84.49 ± 0.36	40.14 ± 0.23	40.48 ± 0.18	40.54 ± 0.13	40.58 ± 0.37
	16		83.32 ± 3.38	84.26 ± 1.11	84.32 ± 0.34	84.33 ± 0.48	40.38 ± 0.15	40.57 ± 0.06	40.64 ± 0.06	40.75 ± 0.3
Human	1		42.77 ± 3.25	43.15 ± 3.14	41.94 ± 3.54	42.0 ± 3.96	39.17 ± 2.53	40.78 ± 2.68	41.05 ± 2.46	41.63 ± 2.68
	4		49.02 ± 1.63	48.41 ± 1.75	50.27 ± 3.85	50.91 ± 2.32	43.26 ± 1.24	44.72 ± 1.1	44.15 ± 1.04	44.37 ± 1.05
	8		53.43 ± 1.83	51.4 ± 1.62	53.92 ± 2.18	53.71 ± 2.06	44.57 ± 0.41	45.59 ± 1.3	44.98 ± 0.91	45.19 ± 1.11
	16		52.48 ± 1.23	51.91 ± 0.19	55.14 ± 3.95	55.22 ± 4.66	45.3 ± 0.98	45.74 ± 0.85	45.19 ± 0.69	45.65 ± 0.92

Table 1: Segmentation performance of EWS and DINO+prototypes utilizing the same annotated pixels.

images, each containing 1, 4, 8, or 16 labeled pixels per image, resulting in 16 distinct experiments per class. The simplest experiment configuration uses only a single labeled pixel, while the most complex involved 16 images with 16 labeled pixels each.

Pixel annotations, however, introduce variability as different pixel or image selection can yield different results. To address this, we ensured that the pixel selection process was randomized (within the ground truth foreground masks) rather than manually done. This is crucial for demonstrating EWS segmentation robustness. Importantly, while the ground truth masks guided pixel selection, they were not used in training. These selected points were then transformed into class prototypes. To enhance reliability, we ran each experiment with 3 different random seeds.

All EWS training experiments utilized a batch size of 16 and the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-4} to facilitate faster convergence. For the STEGO model, we conducted a hyperparameter search to optimize its performance. To ensure a fair

Model	mIoU
STEGO Unsupervised [1]	60.75
STEGO Supervised [1]	85.09
CLIP-ES [9]	72.6
SegGPT [8]	68 ± 12.65
DINO [5] + Prototypes (4 Imgs * 4 Points)	56.87 ± 0.49
DINO [5] + Prototypes (BEST)	58.3 ± 1.12
EWS (4 Imgs * 4 Points)	77.51 ± 0.87
EWS (BEST)	78.23 ± 0.59

Table 2: Comparison of binary semantic segmentation performance across various methods on the Fire dataset.

Model	Construction	Human	Vehicle	Sky	Object	Nature	Flat
Stego Unsupervised [1]	40.66	27.92	26.43	26.26	27.71	39.74	85.88
Stego Supervised [1]	84.34	77.04	85.64	91.17	58.56	89.13	92.66
CLIP-ES [9]	65.35	42.82	67.21	54.28	43.74	75.52	80.14
DINO [5]+Prototypes (4 Imgs - 4 Points)	41.38 ± 0.11	44.72 ± 1.1	40.41 ± 2.67	41.82 ± 0.48	41.32 ± 0.41	40.24 ± 0.37	86.79 ± 0.47
DINO [5]+Prototypes (BEST)	41.59 ± 0.14	45.74 ± 0.85	42.03 ± 0.8	42.46 ± 0.17	43.68 ± 0.45	40.75 ± 0.3	86.94 ± 0.17
EWS (4 Imgs -4 Points)	72.4 ± 1.93	48.41 ± 1.75	78.43 ± 0.92	84.54 ± 0.78	51.8 ± 0.03	85.33 ± 0.88	85.1 ± 2.17
EWS (BEST)	74.8 ± 1.8	55.22 ± 4.66	78.93 ± 0.11	86.32 ± 0.67	56.79 ± 0.38	86.13 ± 0.73	85.65 ± 0.07

Table 3: Comparison of binary semantic segmentation performance across various methods on the Cityscapes dataset.

comparison with the one-shot SegGPT, as SegGPT image prompts we provided the same images as in the 1-image EWS experiment setup. All training experiments were conducted on A5000 GPUs. Performance was evaluated using the mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) metric, which calculates the average IoU for the target class and background.

During training, the EWS contrastive loss thresholds are computed only once per image, because the training images remain unchanged and the thresholds depend solely on the features generated by the frozen DINO backbone. To accelerate the hyperparameter calculation process, we initialized the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) clusters to 0.04 and 0.3, as our experiments show that the majority of clusters are often close to these initial values.

4.4. Results

Table 1 showcases the importance of pixel-point annotations in our method. As can be observed, while the number of images and/or pixel points increases, the model’s performance consistently improves as well. However, the 1Img-1Point configuration has inherent limitations. If the selected point lies on the boundary of the object of interest, the corresponding patch may include background pixels. This can negatively impact segmentation performance, as observed in one of the fire segmentation experiments, where a pixel on the boundary between fire and smoke caused smoke to be incorrectly segmented as the object of interest. Increasing the number of pixel annotations mitigates this limitation by providing more information, as evidenced by the smaller standard deviation in results between the 1Img-1Point and 1Img-4Points configurations (Fire scenario). The inclusion of additional points significantly improves segmentation performance by refining the object’s representation. However, while performance continues to improve as more annotation pixels are added as prompts, the 4Img-4Points configuration proves sufficient to build a model with great performance. Notably, this setup requires minimal annotation effort, with only 4^2 points, and the average performance difference compared to the best-performing configuration across all experiments is a mere -2.4%.

In Tables 2 and 3, we present the performance of the 4Imgs-4Points configuration and the best-performing settings of our model against competing approaches. EWS and DINO+prototype results are extracted from Table 1 which demonstrates the effects of varying the number of images and pixel-point annotations on performance. In the fire segmentation scenario, our model outperforms STEGO-unsupervised by +17% and falls short of STEGO-supervised by only -7%. Notably, EWS also surpasses SegGPT and the wsss method CLIP-ES by +9% and +5.6%, respectively. This improvement is partly due to SegGPT occasionally misclassifying humans or other objects as fire, an issue commonly observed in one-shot segmentation approaches. These approaches tend to bias predictions toward objects frequently seen during training.

For the Cityscapes dataset, our model achieves an average improvement of +35.66% compared to STEGO-unsupervised and demonstrates only a -7.8% difference from STEGO-supervised. This showcases that our approach significantly reduces the per-

Figure 4: A visualization of the segmentation results for all classes tested in this work is presented. The results demonstrate that our method closely resembles Stego (supervised) in terms of visual quality, and both approaches align closely with the ground truth.

formance gap between unsupervised and supervised methods while utilizing the same frozen backbone, ViT-Small (21M parameters). Notably, the Flat class category (e.g., roads) is the only case where DINO+Prototypes slightly outperforms EWS. This can be attributed to the dataset characteristics, where flat surfaces are the most common and frequently occurring objects. Since our method focuses on forming compact clusters, DINO+Prototypes demonstrate better generalization in this specific scenario. However, in all other categories, particularly where objects are less common or larger in size, our approach significantly outperforms the baseline, highlighting its superior effectiveness in diverse contexts. Compared to CLIP-ES, EWS achieves higher performance across all seven category classes, highlighting that pixel-point annotations combined with DINO provide a better source domain representation than text embeddings.

4.5. Ablation study

In addition to Table 1, which showcases model performance with respect to the number of annotated points, we highlight several key observations about our architecture. First, human annotators have the advantage of selecting images and points that are more representative of the dataset. For example, in the fire scenario depicted in

Figure 5: Comparison between a randomly selected fire pixel and a fire pixel manually chosen by a human. We hypothesize that human-selected pixels lead to better prototypes and, consequently, better performance.

Annotator	λ_p	CRF	mIoU
Random	1	-	≈ 62.88
Human	1	-	77.13
Human	0.1	-	79.04
Human	0.1	✓	83.5

Table 4: Ablation study of EWS segmentation performance in the 1Img-1Point configuration.

Fig. 5, the randomly selected image for point annotation is suboptimal. In contrast, we hypothesize that humans are better at selecting images and points that lead to more generalized prototype representations, often resulting in improved model performance.

Second, due to the extensive number of experiments presented in Table 1, we set all loss weights to 1 to simplify the setup and ensure stable training across configurations. While individual experiments may benefit from optimized loss weight values, performing hyperparameter tuning would require access to ground truth masks, which is not aligned with the unsupervised nature of our approach. However, for configurations with very few annotated points (e.g., only one point in the dataset), our experiments indicate that reducing the weight of \mathcal{L}_{proto} can sometimes improve results. Additionally, applying a Conditional Random Field (CRF) as a post-processing step consistently refines the predicted segmentation masks by leveraging the contextual information in the input image, thereby enhancing segmentation quality. In Table 4, we compare the per-

formance of the 1Img-1Point configuration using a randomly selected point versus a human-selected point, as depicted in Fig. 5. We also incorporate a reduced loss weight and CRF post-processing [39] in the comparison.

Our framework, designed for lightweight operation and minimal annotation requirements, achieves approximately 2000 frames per second (FPS) on an NVIDIA A5000 GPU and around 11 FPS on the NVIDIA Xavier NX, making it suitable for edge AI applications. Moreover, all EWS models predicting different classes share the same frozen ViT-Small backbone, pre-trained with the DINO framework. This shared backbone, coupled with the small size and efficient generation of foreground and background maps (where ViT processing accounts for 95% of total inference time), enables the seamless addition of new foreground-background pairs for different classes. This capability allows our framework to be easily extended to multiclass segmentation, offering scalability and versatility for diverse tasks.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we presented EWS, a framework that significantly narrows the gap between unsupervised and supervised segmentation methods while relying on minimal supervision. By leveraging one-pixel annotations as class prototypes and dynamically computing contrastive thresholds, our method achieves robust binary segmentation, even in challenging datasets like Fire and Cityscapes. Remarkably, EWS achieves performance comparable to supervised methods in many cases, using only a few one-pixel annotations across the entire dataset. Its lightweight design, with a frozen ViT-Small backbone and efficient clustering mechanisms, enables real-time inference and scalability, making it ideal for practical applications, including edge computing and emergency response scenarios.

Perhaps the most important limitation of the proposed method is that it has only been evaluated in binary segmentation tasks. Furthermore, our method is affected by the selection of the one-pixel annotations. Some segmentation tasks might feature radically different appearances of the same class objects, that could be encoded as class prototypes. Our proposed method handles this case by automatically tuning its

hyperparameters and by the proposed loss functions, but this does not mean that this is optimal.

In future work, EWS could be extended to the multiclass semantic segmentation case, generating prototypes for different foreground classes. Furthermore, EWS could be extended to leverage dissimilar foreground representations more efficiently, so that they could be used to form "subclasses" of the prototypes. Finally, EWS could be extended to leverage prototypes generated through the integration of text annotations and the multimodal CLIP model.

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